

Human⁺-in-the-Loop to Distill Expert Knowledge into Artificial Intelligence Models: A Survey

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Abstract

Large-scale neural networks have revolutionized many general knowledge areas (e.g., computer vision and language processing), but are still rarely applied in many expert knowledge areas (e.g., healthcare), due to data sparsity and high annotation expenses. Human-in-the-loop machine learning (HIL-ML) incorporates expert domain knowledge into the modeling process, effectively addressing these challenges. Recently, some researchers have started using large models to substitute for certain tasks typically performed by humans. Although large models have limitations in expert knowledge areas, after being trained on trillions of examples, they have demonstrated advanced capabilities in reasoning, semantic understanding, grounding, and planning. These capabilities can serve as proxies of human, which introduces new opportunities and challenges in HIL-ML area. Based on the above, we summary a more comprehensive framework, Human⁺-in-the-Loop Machine Learning (HIL⁺-ML), where Human⁺ represents both humans and large models. HIL⁺-ML can efficiently collaborate human and large model to construct vertical AI models with lower costs. This paper presents the first review of recent advancements in this area. First, we provide a formal definition of HIL⁺-ML and discuss its related fields. Then, we categorize the HIL⁺-ML

methods based on data processing and model development, providing formal definitions for each, and present representative works in detail for each category. Third, we highlight relative applications of HIL⁺-ML. Finally, we summarize the current literature and highlight future research directions. This paper holds significant academic value and has the potential to contribute substantially to existing fields.

Keywords: Human-in-the-Loop, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Large Language Models

1 Introduction

Over the past decade, large-scale neural networks [1] have significantly advanced the development of computer vision, natural language processing, and other general knowledge domains. These breakthroughs, such as applications in image recognition [2], have enabled technologies like autonomous vehicles and facial recognition systems. In the realm of natural language processing, large models like the GPT [3] series and BERT [4] have achieved near-human capabilities in generating and understanding complex texts. These models have not only enhanced the accuracy of machine translation but also improved interactions between users and artificial systems. Furthermore, the adoption of these technologies has driven innovations in intelligent customer service, showcasing their commercial potential.

Despite the remarkable achievements of large-scale neural networks in general knowledge areas, they face numerous challenges in expert domains such as healthcare, law, and so on. These fields often involve highly specialized and sparse datasets that are expensive to acquire and require extensive preprocessing and precise manual annotation to ensure data quality and usability. Additionally, traditional deep learning models are severely tested in their generalization capabilities within these domains [5]. The inability of training data to fully represent the complexities of the real world often means that these models may fail to accurately predict unseen scenarios, thereby limiting their reliability in professional applications. Data privacy becomes crucial when dealing with sensitive personal details in medical or legal contexts [6], demanding extra measures to satisfy regulatory and ethical rules. These challenges demonstrate the need to integrate expert domain knowledge into AI systems, where high accuracy and explainable decision-making processes are necessary for gaining end-user trust. For instance, a medical diagnostic system must be able to clearly justify its recommendations to physicians, allowing them to make informed clinical decisions. Thus, integrating the knowledge and judgment of human experts into the AI model becomes essential.

Facing the challenges above, Human-in-the-Loop Machine Learning (HIL-ML) [7] offers an effective solution by incorporating human knowledge into the machine learning modeling process. As shown in Figure 1, in HIL-ML framework, human can make contributions throughout all stages of machine learning. HIL-ML specifically distill human knowledge into machine learning model, allowing machines to learn from

Fig. 1 The HIL-ML workflow which can be segmented into four main stages: Data Acquisition, Data Processing, Model Development, and Model Optimization, with continuous human involvement throughout the process to ensure iterative refinement and optimization of the models.

human knowledge and experience, thereby minimizing the costs of training an accurate model. By directly distilling deep expert knowledge and understanding into models, the HIL-ML method not only enhances model performance but also improves the explainability of models, making it more transparent and trustworthy to end-users. Additionally, the HIL-ML strategy is crucial for improving model performance on unseen data. Through continuous interaction with experts, the model can better understand and generalize situations that are not well represented in the training data. This approach also reduces potential privacy risks when handling sensitive information, as human experts can directly monitor and adjust the processing of such data. Therefore, HIL-ML not only addresses the limitations of traditional automation methods in professional fields but also enhances the reliability and effectiveness of AI systems in practical operations. By integrating human expert knowledge and feedback, HIL-ML enables AI systems to excel both in technological sophistication and in practical application.

Recently, researchers have begun to employ large models to perform certain tasks traditionally executed by humans [8, 9]. Although these large models hold some limitations in domains requiring expert knowledge, they have demonstrated advanced capabilities in reasoning, semantic understanding, grounding, and planning after being trained on trillions of examples. These capabilities allow large models to act as proxies for human intelligence, thereby introducing new opportunities and challenges in HIL-ML area. However, Current reviews [7, 10, 11] about HIL-ML fail to explore how to address these challenges. Moreover, the potential role of Large Models [12] as participants in HIL-ML has been largely overlooked.

Building on this insight, we survey related works, and summary these concept as an enhanced framework, Human⁺-in-the-Loop Machine Learning (HIL⁺-ML), where Human⁺ includes both human and advanced large-scale models. This framework aims to leverage the complementary strengths of human cognitive skills and machine efficiency. HIL⁺-ML can efficiently collaborate human and large model to construct vertical AI models with lower costs. This paper presents the first review of recent advancements in this area.

This study employs an extensive literature survey method to ensure comprehensive and high-quality research. We have reviewed works published at top computer science and human-computer interaction conferences from 2018 to 2024, such as IJCAI, ACL, KDD, AAAI, NIPS, ICML, CVPR, ICLR, CHI, IMWUT, CSCW and so on. Additionally we have also investigated the latest research on arXiv from 2023 and 2024. By reading titles and abstracts, we selected the most relevant papers, classified them,

Fig. 2 Framework for HIL⁺-ML Methodology which will also be referred to as AIL-ML in the following sections for clarity and conciseness. The framework can be divided into two main phases: Data Acquisition and Processing, and Model Development and Optimization. The first phase contains Data Collection, Initialization, Quality Enhancement, and Annotation. The second phase involves Model Cold Start, Training, and Iterative Enhancement.

and conducted in-depth analyses to ensure a precise understanding of the methods. As shown in Figure 2, the paper begins by defining the core processes of HIL⁺-ML and provides a structured framework for understanding its mechanisms. We then discuss the methodologies used in HIL⁺-ML, emphasizing the critical aspects of data acquisition and processing as well as model development and optimization. We also summarize applications of HIL⁺-ML in domains requiring specialized knowledge. In the last section, we highlight the current challenges within HIL⁺-ML research and outlines future research directions, providing both theoretical and practical guidance for further development in the field. "Human⁺" is a word that we create based on the existing concept of "Human". It is not an officially recognized word. To ensure clarity for readers who may start reading from the latter sections of the paper and might not understand the meaning of "Human⁺", we will also refer to HIL⁺ as "Agent in the

Loop.” The word “agent” carries a clear definition and is easier to comprehend. For convenience in expression throughout the remainder of this paper, we will refer to this framework as Agent-in-the-Loop Machine Learning (AIL-ML) where agents comprise both humans and large models.

This paper contributes significantly to the understanding and practice of HIL⁺-ML by providing new depth and breadth, the contributions of this paper are three-fold:

1. We offer a formal definition of HIL⁺-ML, detailing its structure and how its components work together. Moreover, we explore in depth the role of LLMs in HIL-ML, particularly how they function as intelligent agents within the learning loop and how this integration can improve both model performance and decision-making quality.
2. We offer a detailed classification of data processing and model development methods within HIL⁺-ML, presenting a clear methodological framework for researchers. This classification not only reveals the relationships and differences between various techniques but also highlights the strengths and limitations of each approach in handling specific types of problems.
3. This paper presents a mathematical and formalized description of the HIL⁺-ML framework, simplifying complex concepts and processes to enhance precision in application by researchers and practitioners.

2 Background

2.1 Related Reviews

Human-in-the-loop has emerged as a prominent area of interest within the field of machine learning in recent years. With the expansion of machine learning applications across computer vision, natural language processing, and speech processing, there has been a growing realization that reliance solely on machine-driven learning is limited. Integrating human domain knowledge and experience has proven to be more effective in addressing specific challenges. In the realm of HIL machine learning, several comprehensive review papers have been published, summarizing various techniques, challenges, and future directions within this field. These reviews not only define the various technologies but also discuss the interplay between them, providing researchers with a clear theoretical framework for further exploration.

Xingjiao Wu *et al.* [7] conducted a review of HIL from the perspective of data management. They analyzed existing works on HIL, categorizing them into three progressively related categories: (1) efforts to enhance model performance through data processing, (2) improvements in model performance via interventional model training, and (3) the design of the system independent human-in-the-loop. Furthermore, the paper summarizes applications of HIL and discusses its technical merits and limitations in fields such as natural language processing and computer vision.

Beyond analyzing HIL from a data perspective, there has been significant research interest in the interaction modalities between humans and machine learning algorithms and leveraging these interactions to boost model performance. Eduardo Mosqueira-Rey *et al.* have contributed a thorough overview of this area, defining the forms of HIL

machine learning such as active learning, interactive machine learning, and machine teaching [10]. Their classification hinges on the locus of control within the learning process: active learning with the system in control, interactive machine learning with enhanced user-system interaction, and machine teaching where human experts dictate the learning process. This work provides a delineation of the various interactions and demarcations among different HIL techniques, drawing connections and elucidating their influences. It offers a clear theoretical framework for researchers in the field, laying a foundational theory for the study of HIL.

Although the HIL-ML field has explored various interaction types like demonstrations and preferences, there is a notable lack of comparative analysis or guidelines for selecting the most effective type to solve specific learning problems. Yuchen Cui *et al.* have introduced a set of principles for organizing HIL that examines how different interaction types affect human performance and the quality of training data [13]. In addition, they discuss strategies for selecting the most effective interaction type for particular learning issues and identify ongoing open questions in the field.

While previous reviews have comprehensively addressed the techniques, challenges, and prospects of HIL-ML, the advent of large models has introduced new dynamics and challenges into the HIL landscape. To address this evolution, we have reviewed related works and consolidated these insights into an updated framework, AIL, which integrates both human expertise and sophisticated large-scale models.

2.2 Related Research Areas

There are several research fields closely related to AIL-ML, including but not limited to: HIL-ML, Large Model, active learning and knowledge distillation. We briefly describe them in the following.

Human-in-the-loop Machine learning [7, 10, 13] is a method that integrates human knowledge to guide and enhance machine learning models. In HIL-ML framework, human participants contribute inputs not only during data preprocessing, model training, and performance evaluation stages but also engage in interactive feedback throughout the entire machine learning workflow. This approach emphasizes the collaborative interaction between humans and algorithms with the goal of optimizing the learning process, thereby improving the accuracy, interpretability, and reliability of the models. HIL-ML is particularly suited for tasks that are too complex for automated systems or require human intuition.

Large Model [12?] typically refers to a type of machine learning model characterized by a substantial number of parameters, often scaling into the billions. These models, also known as large-scale models or foundation models [14], are designed to process and generate data across various tasks and domains. They leverage deep learning techniques and are predominantly neural network architectures such as transformers [15], which allow them to achieve state-of-the-art performance in areas like natural language processing, computer vision. Large models are famous for their ability to learn complex patterns and relationships within data, which facilitates advanced reasoning and generalization capabilities beyond specific tasks, contributing significantly to advancements in artificial intelligence.

Active Learning [10, 16] is a machine learning approach where the learner (often a model) selectively queries an oracle (typically a human annotator acting as a teacher) to label examples that are ambiguous but likely to provide significant insights to the learning process. This targeted approach allows the learner to enhance its performance with fewer training examples. Active Learning is particularly effective in environments rich in unlabeled data where the annotation task is costly or time-consuming. This method strategically reduces the volume of data that needs labeling while maximizing learning efficiency and effectiveness. Active Learning is indeed a method within HIL-ML.

Knowledge Distillation [17–19] is a technique where knowledge is transferred from a larger, more complex model (often called the teacher) to a smaller, simpler model (often called the student). The goal of knowledge distillation is to enable the student model to achieve performance comparable to the teacher model, but with reduced computational complexity and memory requirements. This is particularly useful for deploying high-performing models on devices with limited resources, such as mobile phones and embedded systems. Knowledge distillation has become a popular method for model compression and is extensively used to enhance the efficiency of deploying deep learning models in resource-constrained environments.

3 Theory

In the evolution of machine learning, HIL-ML has emerged as a pivotal methodology. By integrating human insight into the machine learning workflow, HIL-ML plays a crucial role in the data processing and model training of machine learning [7]. Within this framework, humans are connected to the model loop in a specific method, allowing machines to learn from human knowledge and experience. This integration not only enhances model accuracy but also significantly reduces the costs of model training [20]. Through human involvement, HIL-ML utilizes human knowledge for corrections and optimizations at various stages, resulting in more precise and reliable machine learning models [10].

Large models have a wide range of knowledge and strong reasoning skills similar to those of humans. They understand contexts deeply, which allows them to generate and comprehend language almost like humans do [21]. Based on these strengths, we propose a new concept called Large Model in the Loop Machine Learning (LMIL-ML). LMIL-ML leverages the extensive knowledge and inferential power of large models, such as GPT [3], Lora [22], Llama [23] and so on, embedding them into the machine learning model loop. This approach enables the learning and distillation of large model expertise during the training process. LMIL-ML offers efficient automated support in data handling and model training, enabling the training of highly accurate machine learning models at minimal cost. Similar to HIL-ML, the goal of LMIL-ML is to enhance model accuracy and training efficiency by leveraging the capabilities of large models, minimizing costs.

Based on the frameworks of HIL-ML and LMIL-ML, we further introduce a more comprehensive framework, Agent in the Loop Machine Learning (AIL-ML) which is

also called Human⁺-in-the-Loop Machine Learning (HIL⁺-ML). In the AIL-ML framework, agents include both humans and large models. By embedding agents into the machine learning model loop in specific ways, the machine learning models can learn from the agents’ knowledge and analytical reasoning. AIL-ML harnesses human intuition and knowledge along with the computational and inferential capabilities of large models, employing a complementary synergy of strengths. Agents play roles in data processing, model training, and optimization at each stage, thereby building highly accurate machine learning models at minimal cost. The introduction of AIL-ML not only improves model performance but also enhances its adaptability and robustness in complex tasks.

Let M_t represent the state of the machine learning model at time t , and D_t denote the dataset used for training or updating the model at the same iteration. Agents A_t , comprising both human H_t and large model L_t , contribute to the model’s learning process by providing feedback and insights based on the data and the current state of the model.

The agent’s impact on the model can be represented by the following equation:

$$A(D_t, M_t) = \alpha H(D_t, M_t) + \beta L(D_t, M_t) \quad (1)$$

Where:

- α and β are weighting factors that balance the contributions of human and large model agents, respectively.
- $H(D_t, M_t)$ is the feedback function representing the contribution of human intuition and knowledge, assessing and influencing the model based on the given data and its current performance.
- $L(D_t, M_t)$ is the feedback function for the large model, providing computational and inferential insights based on its analytical capabilities.

The model update function can be represented as follows:

$$M_{t+1} = M_t + \eta A(D_t, M_t) \quad (2)$$

Where:

- η is the learning rate, controlling the extent to which the agent feedback modifies the model.

4 Methodology

This section will provide a detailed introduction to the implementation of AIL-ML. As shown in Figure 3, we categorize the existing work into two main parts: data acquisition and processing, and model development and optimization.

In data acquisition and processing, we discuss several key steps: first, during the data collection stage, we explain how agents participate in and optimize the data collection process [8, 20, 24, 34, 47, 52, 54, 65, 73, 75]; second, in the data initialization

Fig. 3 Taxonomy of Agent-in-the-Loop Machine Learning.

stage, we explore how agents transform collected raw data into formats suitable for machine learning [40, 41, 48, 60, 63, 74]; next, during the data quality enhancement stage, we introduce how agents help improve the quality of data [9, 20, 32, 35, 52, 53, 56, 57, 57, 58, 67–73]; finally, in the data annotation stage, we explore how agents use their knowledge for precise and effective data labeling [8, 9, 13, 20, 24, 26, 41, 47, 48, 52, 53, 56–66].

In the model development and optimization part, the focus is on three core segments: firstly, we discuss how AIL-ML strategies effectively address the model cold start problem [8, 9, 32, 34, 47–55]; secondly, during the model training phase, we detail how agents’ advanced knowledge is used to calibrate model parameters and optimize the learning framework [39–46]; and lastly, in the model iterative enhancement phase, we emphasize how continual intervention and feedback from agents incrementally enhance the performance of machine learning models through multiple iterations [20, 24–38].

By introducing the AIL-ML concept, we effectively leverage the strengths of human and large models to construct efficient, accurate, and adaptable machine learning models. Agents play a pivotal role in data acquisition and processing, as well as in model development and optimization. This strategy of combining human wisdom with machine power offers a new possibility for constructing efficient, precise machine learning models, pushing the technology to higher levels of achievement.

4.1 Data Acquisition and Processing

In the field of machine learning, data and models are intricately linked. The collection and initialization of data directly influence the construction and performance of models. Moreover, enhancing data quality is crucial for the iterative improvement of models. This interaction between data and models forms a mutually beneficial relationship, highlighting the importance of data quality in improving model performance. In this section, we investigate AIL-ML techniques that focus on optimizing the entire data lifecycle in machine learning. This includes a detailed examination of methods in the areas of *Data Collection*, *Data Initialization*, *Data Quality Enhancement*, and *Data Annotation*.

4.1.1 Data Collection

In this section, we explore the data collection mechanisms within the AIL-ML framework, where agents can be humans, large models, or a combination of both. Agents play a crucial role in generating diverse, comprehensive, and representative data sets, essential for training complex machine learning models. This not only broadens the scope of training data but also enhances the model’s generalization capabilities and adaptability to complex environments.

Research analysis indicates that the AIL-ML framework utilizes three primary data collection strategies, each corresponding to different stages of the machine model’s lifecycle. These strategies include data collection before model construction, during model construction, and after the model construction.

Before model construction, data collection is suitable for the following two scenarios. Firstly, these strategies are suitable for tasks that require highly specific data and lack large-scale public datasets [75]. For example, in the Internet of Things (IoT) context, various sensors are positioned at different locations. Due to the lack of public dataset, researchers need to collect the data. It is essential that the data should be not only abundant but also diverse and representative, to effectively capture the diverse potential states of the real-world environment. For instance, Shruthi K. Hiremath *et al.* [47] demonstrates how data is passively observed and collected through sensor networks installed in different locations within smart home systems. This network, containing door sensors, motion sensors, and temperature sensors, continuously monitors environmental changes and logs events with timestamps and sensor IDs. The data, stored in event logs on local servers or in the cloud, forms the basis for subsequent processing and analysis. Similarly, Jason Wu *et al.* [20] presented a system that automatically collects environmental sound signals through smart speakers. This system utilizes unsupervised clustering techniques to identify recurring activity types. Once the system can identify specific activities with high confidence, it starts a one-shot interaction with users through voice commands. This interaction is used to label these activities and create a labeled dataset. This approach allows the system to improve the accuracy of environmental sound recognition incrementally through continue learning and in-situ training, without the need for predefined data. Consequently, it develops an accurate, environment-specific, acoustic signal-based activity recognition model.

Secondly, these strategies are suitable for tasks leveraging large models for data generation. Trained on vast amounts of data, large models have accumulated extensive general knowledge and demonstrated remarkable abilities in reasoning and analysis. This allows researchers to use large models to generate high-quality data, significantly reducing the time and costs. This enables both individuals and small organizations to utilize advanced AI technologies more effectively. Through well-designed prompt engineering, researchers can direct large models to generate specific datasets on demand, optimizing both the training process and model performance. B Ding *et al.* [8] proposed an approach named Prompt-Guided Training Data Generation (PGDG). This method leverages the generative capabilities of GPT-3 to produce labeled data pairs directly from specific prompts, significantly enhancing the efficiency and quality of data generation. For tasks such as sentiment analysis and relationship extraction, the data generated through this method matches or even surpasses the quality of manually annotated data with reducing time and cost. Additionally, large models can generate diverse data using seed datasets. In [34], C Xu *et al.* detailed how to use seed datasets to collect high-quality, multi-turn dialogue data through self-chat. They chose platforms like Quora and Stack Overflow as seed datasets. These platforms provide a wealth of user-generated questions that guide the generation of dialogues by ChatGPT, which simulates both sides of a conversation. Each dialogue began with a seed question and naturally progressed through several rounds of exchanges until it ended. To ensure the quality and format of the dialogues, researchers used predefined templates to control the dialogue generation process. This method not only addresses the scarcity of high-quality, multi-turn dialogue but also offers a practical solution due to its efficiency and relatively low cost. To further enhance the diversity and quality of the generated data, researchers have designed various generation strategies [54, 65, 73], such as Greedy Search, Top-k Sampling, and Nucleus Sampling. These strategies aim to improve the diversity and quality of the generated text. Such innovative techniques ensure that the data generated is both varied and of high quality, suitable for training robust models.

During model construction, the continuous collection of data through agents can enable the model to better adapt and learn under complex or unfamiliar environmental conditions. Moreover, this can make model identify potential biases. In [24], data collection spans the entire lifecycle of the dialogue model, particularly post-deployment. Through real-time interactions with users, the system continuously collects new training data, including Human-Bot (HB) dialogue data and user feedback data. When the model assesses high user satisfaction in a conversation, the user’s responses are recorded as HB dialogue data. Correspondingly, when the model anticipates potential errors, it requests feedback from users, which is then used to refine the model. This collected data, after processing and storage, is regularly utilized for retraining the model, enabling it to continually learn and improve in practical applications, thereby enhancing conversational abilities and user satisfaction. This approach not only reduces the dependency on manually annotated data but also allows the model to rapidly adapt to new conversational contexts, significantly improving user experience and model performance.

After model construction, the collection of data from agents can allow model to handle new types of tasks. For example, in gesture recognition systems, allowing users to personalize their gestures can enhance gesture memorability, increase interaction efficiency, and improve accessibility for individuals with specific needs. X Xu *et al.* propose a framework for gesture customization using few-shot learning, where users provide only a few custom gesture examples to the system [52]. This method enables the system to recognize customized gestures with high accuracy without compromising the performance of existing gestures. Specifically, users record new gestures on a smartwatch interface, and the system guides them through data collection via an interactive interface. The system continuously monitors performance and provides feedback to users. If the model’s accuracy falls below expectations, the system guides users to record more samples to further optimize the model.

Data collection in the AIL-ML framework can be described as follows:

$$x_t = f(D_t, M_t, A_t) \quad (3)$$

Where:

- x_t represents the data generated by the agent at time t ,
- D_t and M_t represent the current data set and model state, respectively,
- A_t denotes the actions or decisions of the agent at time t , which may include inputs from humans H_t and large models L_t ,
- f is a function defining how data is generated based on the current data set, model state, agent state, and actions.

Additionally, the process by which agents generate data based on given labels can be formalized through a conditional probability model, formulated as

$$x_t = p(x | y, D_t, M_t, A_t) \quad (4)$$

where:

- x_t is the data generated by the agent at time t ,
- y is the provided label,
- $p(x | y, D_t, M_t)$ is a conditional probability distribution indicating the likelihood of generating data x given the label y , current data set D_t , and model state M_t .

These formulations offer a comprehensive description of data collection under the AIL-ML framework, illustrating how to utilize agents’ internal state, model state, and available data, along with potential external labels, to acquire data. This highlights the dynamic and adaptive nature of AIL-ML.

4.1.2 Data Initialization and Preprocessing

Data initialization and preprocessing are crucial steps that transform raw data into a format suitable for machine learning models. In this section, we will introduce the AIL-ML techniques that initialize and preprocess data through agents.

Upon reviewing AIL-ML literature, we identify two main methodologies that utilize agents for data initialization and preprocessing. These methodologies leverage agents to perform data analysis [42, 48, 60, 74] or to develop effective feature representation [40, 41, 63].

Data analysis by agents involves examining large datasets to discern underlying patterns and valuable insights that are not immediately apparent. This process is vital for preparing data in a way that significantly enhances the training and performance of machine learning models. Shanshan Zhang *et al.* [48] employed a high-recall regular expression to detect potential entity candidates within texts. Initially, experts design preliminary regular expressions suitable for specific entity extraction tasks, such as dates, email addresses, and course numbers, aiming to capture most target entities. Then, these expressions are used to scan documents, extracting all matching substrings. Each matched substring is expanded to include surrounding text, providing sufficient contextual information for its validation as a target entity. This method creates a collection of candidate substrings, encompassing all potential entities, significantly narrowing the scope of text that needs further processing and thereby enhancing the efficiency of subsequent annotation and model training. For tasks that require expert knowledge, the AIL-ML strategy distills the deep knowledge and understanding of human experts into ML models through data analysis. Chihcheng Hsieh *et al.* [60] leveraged expert knowledge in the data initialization and preprocessing stages. They utilize chest X-ray images, eye tracking data from radiologists, and patients' clinical data. The eye tracking data, which includes gaze points and sequences during the diagnostic process, is mapped to image coordinates to extract the visual search patterns of the radiologists. Concurrently, clinical data is encoded and standardized to align dimensionally with 3D image data, and expanded through convolution layers for effective integration with image data. Through these steps, the diagnostic behaviors and knowledge of human experts are effectively distilled into the model, enabling it to learn from the experts' diagnostic processes.

On the other hand, agents are used for feature representation, which transforms raw data into a structured format more suitable for subsequent algorithmic processing. This transformation ensures that the data are formatted to maximize the efficiency and accuracy of the machine learning model. In [40], agents' interaction and feedback play important roles in feature representation. Users annotate video frames, for instance by delineating foreground and background, providing essential feature information. These annotations are used to generate object masks and serve as feature inputs to help the network identify and represent foreground objects. The user-provided data is then encoded into a format suitable for network processing, such as binary masks representing positive and negative examples. The interaction network combines this information with video frame data and transforms it through a feature encoding module into high-dimensional features suitable for model processing. Ultimately, these encoded data are integrated into a multi-channel input tensor for the interaction and

propagation networks, ensuring the model effectively utilizes the initial information provided by users to enhance performance and prediction accuracy.

Furthermore, agents can optimize feature representation. Hannes Kath *et al.* [41] presented an interactive machine learning tool for annotating passive acoustic monitoring datasets created for wildlife monitoring. Users can select data points within a state-space representation and create new boundaries, further refining feature representation. Through real-time feedback, the model dynamically adjusts feature representations and prediction outcomes, gradually improving accuracy with each retraining cycle. Carrie J. Cai *et al.* [63] developed tools that helped pathologists cope with the shortcomings of deep learning algorithms during image retrieval. These tools are designed to adjust retrieval algorithms in real time to better meet the diagnostic needs of doctors and enhance their trust in the algorithms. While using the SMILY system, pathologists refine and optimize image feature representations through tools like regional, example-based, and conceptual refinement. These tools allow pathologists to emphasize or remove irrelevant features, ensuring the model focuses on correct diagnostic features. This process of real-time interaction and feedback can be seen as a dynamic method of data preprocessing, aiding in the improvement of the model’s feature representation.

How to utilize agents for data initialization and preprocessing can be described as follows:

$$F_t = \psi(D_t, A_t, P_f) \quad (5)$$

where:

- F_t represents the feature set derived at time t ,
- as defined previously, D_t and A_t continue to denote the current data set and the agent’s actions or decisions,
- function ψ serves as a data transformation function, incorporating all essential preprocessing steps such as data cleaning, normalization, and feature extraction,
- P_f stands for the set of preprocessing parameters.

4.1.3 Data Quality Enhancement

Data quality is important for model training and its subsequent performance. In this section, we explore AIL-ML methods related to enhance data quality. By identifying and correcting discrepancies, biases, and errors in raw data, agents significantly enhance the precision and consistency of the data. Moreover, agents play a key role in augmenting the diversity and richness of data.

There are two primary AIL methodologies by which agents can enhance data quality: 1) improving data precision or consistency, [20, 32, 39, 56, 57, 70, 73, 76] and 2) increasing data diversity [9, 52, 58, 67–69, 72].

The first methodology focuses on improving the accuracy and consistency of the data. For machine learning, enhancing data precision and consistency can improve model performance. The knowledge and analytical capabilities of agents can significantly augment data accuracy, thereby enhancing model precision. In the context of

smart home environments, Sungjae Cho *et al.* [70] introduced a novel strategy named AI-to-Human (AHA), which actively modifies environmental conditions to enhance the inferential accuracy of AI models. Unlike traditional smart devices, such as embedded vision AI sensors that passively monitor resident activities, AHA actively induces resident behaviors, facilitating more reliable AI inferences. Initially, AI sensors detect poor perception conditions, such as orientations away from the camera or distances too close or too far from the camera. Then, the AHA system employs smart home devices like speakers, displays, or ambient lighting to unremarkably guide resident behavior into more favorable perceptual conditions. The AHA system effectively improves data quality and overcomes the common challenges of passive perception inherent in traditional methods. Similarly, Listen Learner [20] system employs an active learning approach that enhances data quality through various interactive strategies with users, including open-ended questions, confirmation questions, and refinement questions. When a new event falls into the decision boundary of model, the system will ask a choice question as a confirmation questions. This not only reduces cognitive load on users but also enhances the quality of data, adapting dynamically to different environmental sounds, thus improving data precision and the accuracy of classification models. Furthermore, some AIL-ML methods enhance data precision by incorporating human reasoning. For instance, the MARTA framework [39] introduces human rationales combined with Bayesian methods to assess agent reliability, thereby enhancing data precision quality. Agents provide not only document labels but also rational segments supporting these labels. During training, the model weights these rational segments based on agent reliability, ensuring that high-quality rational segments contribute more.

Researchers have implemented various methods to manage and control the quality of agent annotations. In LSUN [56], annotation quality control is achieved through several strategies including redundant annotations, quality checks and detailed annotation guidelines. Specifically, each item is annotated by at least two independent annotators to ensure consistency in the results. Items with known label are embedded within the annotation tasks to monitor the annotators' performance. Both online and offline quality control mechanisms ensure that annotators deliver high-quality results. Detailed annotation guidelines and examples help annotators understand the requirements of the task clearly. Together, these methods ensure high quality and consistency of the annotated data.

Some researchers employed agents to identify and correct discrepancies, biases, and errors in raw data, significantly enhancing data consistency and model accuracy. Jiayuan Gao *et al.* [76] proposed LLMIE-UHAR, which leverages Large Language Models (LLMs) and Iterative Evolution for Unsupervised Human Activity Recognition. This method capitalizes on the logical reasoning capabilities of LLMs to detect inconsistencies within datasets. This is particularly important for unsupervised learning where labels are absent. The effectiveness of LLMIE-UHAR shows the potential of LLMs to improve data quality in real-world applications. This capability of agents to augment data quality forms a critical component in the development of more robust, efficient, and reliable machine learning systems.

There are some AIL methods which enhance data precision by reducing data noise. Riku Arakawa *et al.* [32] proposed PrISM-Tracker, which incorporates human

input to manage data uncertainty. This framework actively interacts with user input when model predictions are uncertain, effectively reducing noise and uncertainty of data. Particularly in smart home environments, where sensor data may be noisy or the sequences of actions unclear. Additionally, to address the challenge of initial low-quality data generation by large models, Jiahui Gao *et al.* [73] introduced the SUNGEN framework, which uses language models to generate synthetic data with task descriptions and label information. This initial data often includes samples with incorrect labels or irrelevant content that can lead to model overfitting and reduced generalization. The SUNGEN framework fix this by employing a dual-layer optimization process: an inner loop optimizes model parameters using weighted cross-entropy loss, while an outer loop uses a noise-robust loss function to evaluate model performance on a synthetic validation set. This iterative process refines sample weights, enhancing the selection of high-quality data.

The second methodology emphasizes broadening the range of data variability, which is vital for training robust models capable of performing well across diverse scenarios. Enhancing the diversity of data can not only improve the generalization ability but also ensure superior performance on unseen samples of machine learning models.

Synthetic data generation is a prevalent method for enhancing data diversity in machine learning. This approach involves creating new data based on the characteristics of existing data to increase the diversity of the data available for model training. Zhe Liu *et al.* [58] introduced a method for global feature contribution analysis, which combined human evaluation to identify error features of the model. This method performs a local feature contribution analysis and quantifies each feature’s contribution. Subsequently, it calculates the global contributions of each feature to identify those with significant impacts on model predictions. Agents are employed to annotate and verify these global features, evaluating their contribution and correctness. This methodology not only improves the generalization capabilities of the data but also model’s performance on unseen data, enhancing the robustness and reliability of model’s. Moreover, large models can synthesize data to increase diversity. In [9], after employing Chain-of-Thought prompting techniques, large models generate natural language inferences that include both the final labels and detailed intermediary steps and logical explanations, providing richer and more useful training data for smaller models. The inferential content generated by large models significantly improves the context and detail quality of the training data.

By adding small perturbations to the original samples, adversarial examples can greatly reduce the accuracy of the original classifier and achieve the purpose of anti-deep learning [77]. Because past approaches expose superficial patterns, the resulting adversarial examples are limited in complexity and diversity. To address these shortcomings, Eric Wallace *et al.* [68] proposed an AIL-ML framework for generating adversarial examples. Researchers have applied this generation framework to a question answering task called Quizbowl, where trivia enthusiasts craft adversarial questions. The questions generated within this framework were tested through live human-computer matches, demonstrating that while these questions appeared ordinary to human participants, they systematically stump neural and information retrieval models. Agent-involved adversarial example generation is effectiveness, which

not only increases the diversity and complexity of the data but also enhances the models’ generalization capabilities [69].

Data augmentation plays a pivotal role in enhancing data diversity. Xuhai Xu *et al.* [52] has developed a user-defined gesture recognition framework that requires participants to provide few custom gesture examples. After acquiring these gestures, the system employs multiple data augmentation methods to generate additional samples: 1) zooming, to simulate different gesture speed; scaling, to simulate different gesture strength; time-warping, to simulate gesture temporal variance. Thus, these augmented samples increase the diversity and of the data. Additionally, large models, pre-trained on extensive datasets, have been fine-tuned with reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) to generate text similar to human expression. Haixing Dai *et al.* [72] utilized large models to generate diverse and high-quality textual data as data augmentation, which rephrases each sentence in the training samples into multiple conceptually similar but semantically different samples. The augmented samples can then be used in downstream model training. Data augmented through large models significantly boosts performance in few-shot learning tasks. This efficient and practical data augmentation method reduces reliance on manual annotation. This data augmentation method is efficient and practical, reducing reliance on manual annotations.

These strategies demonstrate how researchers utilize AIL methods to realize data in data quality enhancement for machine learning, ensuring that models are not only trained on high-quality data but also adaptable to complex real-world environment.

To explain how agents enhance data quality within AIL-ML framework, we employ a formalized notation system to construct a mathematical model. The enhanced dataset at time t can be represented as:

$$D_{\text{enhanced},t} = \theta(D_t, A_t, Q) \quad (6)$$

where:

- $D_{\text{enhanced},t}$ denotes the dataset at time t after data quality enhancement,
- as defined previously, D_t and A_t continue to denote the current data set and the agent’s actions or decisions,
- Q represents a set of parameters for data quality enhancement, defining specific quality control operations,
- θ is the data quality enhancement function, responsible for executing specific data improvement actions.

4.1.4 Data Annotation

In the realms of deep learning and machine learning, data annotation is fundamentally crucial due to the dependency of model learning capabilities on extensive, high-quality, annotated datasets. In this section, we introduce AIL-ML methods specifically aimed at enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of data annotation.

Initially, we present an overview of the current practices of agent-based annotation within AIL framework, outlining how agents contribute to the data labeling process. Then, we explore various methodologies focus on reducing annotation costs and increasing the efficiency of the annotation process. The integration of these strategies ensures that the data annotation is not only cost-effective but also enhances the scalability and applicability of machine learning models in different applications.

Fig. 4 Classification of annotation methods based on the degree of freedom. The fixed-choice method provides minimal freedom with predefined options for selection. Range selection allows choosing within discrete or continuous sequences, offering more flexibility. The open input method provides the highest degree of freedom, allowing free text input.

As illustrated in Figure 4, the common methods used for annotation can be classified into three types based on the degree of freedom each method provides: fixed-choice, range selection, and open input.

- The fixed-choice method, which offers the least freedom, requires agents to select from at least two predefined options. This is the most commonly used and universally applicable annotation method, offering minimal cognitive burden to agents but lacking flexibility compared to other methods [20].
- Range selection, offering more freedom than fixed-choice, includes choosing within discrete or continuous sequences. Discrete sequences consist of clearly distinguishable units, such as text, while continuous sequences, like image pixels or signal durations, lack clear units [52, 63]. In these instances, individual data points may not contain complete meaning on their own (e.g., pixels). For some unstructured data, researchers utilize dimension reduction to visualize the data on a graphical interface, allowing agents to select ranges by drawing boundary boxes on spectrograms to manually annotate events [41].
- The open input method provides the highest degree of freedom, where agents can input self-defined text. This method enables the generation of rich, diverse annotations, such as dialogues [24] or rules [48]. Open input annotations are particularly

beneficial for tasks requiring complex data interpretation, allowing agents to offer detailed information that enhances model training and performance.

The reduction of annotation costs within the AIL-ML framework is a prominent research focus. Annotation for certain tasks can be costly, demanding considerable time, energy, and expertise from annotators. As described in Figure 5, the AIL-ML framework utilizes three kinds of strategies to reduce annotation costs:

1. **Data:** selecting the most valuable samples for annotation to reduce the number of items needing labels.
2. **Process Optimization:** optimizing the annotation process to enhance efficiency.
3. **Agent:** deploying hierarchical levels of agents to carry out these tasks, thereby diminishing the overall annotation costs.

Fig. 5 Three primary strategies for reduce annotation costs within the AIL=ML framework. The strategies include: selecting the most valuable data samples, optimizing data interaction processes and leveraging diverse agents.

In the context of enhancing efficiency in machine learning, selecting the most valuable samples for agents to annotate can significantly reduce the number of data points that need to be labeled. One effective approach is the cluster-then-label method, which reduces the volume of data needing annotation by selecting representative samples for labeling, as discussed in the works of Wu *et al.* [20] and Hiremath *et al.* [47]. This approach uses unsupervised clustering to identify key data points that are then annotated, thus diminishing the overall volume of data requiring manual labels. In scenarios where the system can accurately recognize certain activities, it may initiate a one-shot interaction for annotating such behaviors, thereby creating a labeled dataset. Data points with low confidence or high uncertainty in current ML models are deemed highly informative and prioritized for annotation. In parallel, Qian *et al.* introduced the PARTNER system [26], which predicts labels for all unannotated entities using the current model and ranks them based on uncertainty, focusing annotation efforts on the most uncertain instances. Following annotation, similar instances are identified and assigned pseudo-labels based on the annotated data, thereby augmenting the training dataset efficiently. This strategy effectively combines user involvement with model training, minimizing the need for extensive manual annotations. Furthermore,

boundary samples present classification challenges due to inherent features of multiple categories. To address this, Sahu *et al.* [65] introduced a method where large models re-annotate boundary samples to ensure accurate classification, thus enhancing both the accuracy and generalization capability of the training models.

Optimizing the annotation process to reduce workload and cost while enhancing efficiency is also a key focus in current research. Jan-Christoph Klie *et al.* [59] have effectively utilized recommendation algorithms to propose potential concepts and adaptively prioritize candidates. Their approach has proven to increase the speed of annotation by 35%, with users expressing a strong preference for this system. Similarly, in the LSUN project led by Fisher Yu [56], the development of an efficient graphical user interface significantly lightens the annotation load and enhances productivity. This interface focuses the annotator on a single image at a time, providing thumbnails of previous and next images to ease understanding and reduce navigation time. Enhancements such as full-screen image display improve the visibility of visual details, leading to more accurate annotations. Moreover, the introduction of simplified keyboard shortcuts, like using the space bar for classification, greatly enhances the efficiency of operations. These interface innovations not only boost the efficiency of data annotation but also substantially lower the costs involved, providing robust support for building extensive image datasets.

In the context of Agent in the Loop Machine Learning, agents can be categorized into three distinct types: LLMs, general users, and domain experts. As shown in figure 6, general users hold general knowledge, which is broad and encompasses a wide array of basic facts across various domains. LLMs, on the other hand, are trained on trillions of data points from extensive databases, encompassing not only general knowledge but also a significant amount of database-specific information. Domain experts stand out by their possession of both general knowledge and highly specialized expert knowledge, specific to their particular field of study. It is important to note that the knowledge capacity of LLMs is limited by the nature of their training data, which is generated by humans and may not cover the depth of expertise that domain experts achieve through specialized education and experience. Thus, the knowledge ceiling of LLMs is typically considered to be below that of domain experts.

Upon training with datasets consisting of trillions of data points, LLMs have developed capabilities that include reasoning, semantic understanding, grounding, and planning. These capabilities suggest that LLMs could serve effectively as proxies for humans in AIL contexts, potentially reducing the substantial costs associated with manual labor [9, 64]. Researchers like Shuohang Wang [53] have explored the use of GPT-3 as a cost-effective tool for data annotation. By generating pseudo-labels through GPT-3, this approach offers a more economical and faster alternative to traditional manual labeling methods. Compared to manual annotation, the use of GPT-3 can reduce costs by 50% to 96%, owing to its ability to generate labels more swiftly and at a lower cost.

Various studies have explored strategies for distributing annotation tasks among different agent types, employing a multi-level agent architecture to lower annotation costs effectively [35, 71]. LLMs show considerable efficacy in handling tasks with limited label spaces, significantly reducing manual annotation costs and reaching quality

Fig. 6 Three types of agents in the AIL-ML framework: general users, LLMs, and domain experts. General users hold general knowledge across various domains. LLMs are enhanced by training on extensive databases, holding both general and substantial database-specific knowledge. Domain experts, combine general knowledge and expert knowledge, establishing them at the highest level of knowledge within their specific fields.

levels akin to human annotations under specific conditions. However, their performance is less robust in scenarios with extensive labeling requirements and complex relationships [8]. To optimize both cost and quality, integrating LLMs with human annotators proves beneficial, particularly for critical tasks. Shuohang Wang and his team [53] have leveraged GPT-3 to generate pseudo-labels and their corresponding confidence scores, allowing for selective human re-annotation of labels that demonstrate low confidence. This strategy significantly decreases the dependency on human resources without compromising the quality of annotations, which is particularly critical when working within limited budgets on large-scale datasets. While LLMs offer efficiency and cost savings in generating annotations, their performance on complex or domain-specific tasks is typically flawed and may introduce biases relative to human annotations. To address these challenges, Xinru Wang *et al.* [66] have introduced a collaborative method that utilizes the strengths of LLMs and human annotators to enhance annotation accuracy and reliability at low costs. This approach involves LLMs producing initial labels and explanations, followed by a validation model that evaluates these labels, with human annotators subsequently focusing on the instances scored lowest by the validation model. The LLM-generated explanations provide additional context that aids human annotators in refining and improving the labels, thus ensuring high-quality annotations in a cost-effective manner.

In recent studies, expert agents have been utilized to create rules that significantly decrease the amount of data that needs to be annotated, thereby reducing costs associated with data labeling [48, 57]. Shanshan Zhang *et al.* [48] developed a method where human experts use regular expressions to establish initial rules, generating weakly labeled data. While this data might contain noise, it serves as a valuable asset for the early stages of model training, particularly effective when labeled data are scarce. This approach accelerates the annotation process, improving the quality of ML models. However, when there is an abundance of labeled data, deep neural networks excel at uncovering more intricate dependencies in the data. Data derived from regular expressions typically show limited diversity and are strongly rule-oriented, making

them suitable primarily in the early stages of model training where labels are deficient. Patrick Hemmer *et al.* [61] have explored a coordinated approach between classifier systems and expert agents. In their system, classifiers are trained to pinpoint cases that are difficult for human experts to handle, while an assignment system efficiently allocates each case to the most suitable agent, whether human or machine. This approach has been evaluated in several studies, including experiments with "synthetic" experts and a real medical dataset annotated by multiple radiologists. Research indicates that this method outperforms previous approaches and provides more accurate results than either the best human experts or classifiers alone.

The agent-assisted data annotation process within the AIL-ML framework can be modeled as an optimization problem, formulated by the following equation:

$$L_t = \gamma(D'_t, A_t, \Sigma_t, \Omega_t) \quad (7)$$

where:

- L_t represents the outputs at time t , which may include labels, confidence levels, and explanations based on the output options Ω_t .
- D'_t denotes the subset of samples selected from the original dataset D_t for annotation.
- A_t is the inputs from the agent.
- Σ_t is a set of annotation strategies, such as fixed-choice, range selection, or open input, and how these strategies are implemented to reduce costs and increase efficiency.
- Ω_t defines the output options, specifying which additional information should be generated.
- γ is the comprehensive annotation function responsible for generating the desired annotated data based on the selected samples S_t , agent inputs A_t , the annotation strategies Σ_t and the output options Ω_t .

This formulation ensures that the data annotation process is not only cost-effective but also scalable and applicable to various machine learning models in different applications. By incorporating intelligent agent strategies, AIL-ML systems can enhance efficiency and reduce costs associated with data annotation.

4.2 Model Development and Optimization

For machine learning, the development and optimization of models are also important. The methodologies adopted during the model development phase significantly impact the effectiveness and efficiency. Moreover, continual refinement and optimization are essential for the enhancement of model performance. In this section, we investigate AIL-ML techniques that concentrate on model development and optimization. This includes a comprehensive analysis of methods in the areas of *Model Cold Start Issue*, *Model Training* and *Model Iterative Enhancement*.

4.2.1 Model Cold Start Issues

In machine learning, the model cold start problem refers to the challenge of initializing a model effectively when minimal or no historical data is available. This issue is particularly prevalent for machine learning that is data-driven. The lack of initial training data can significantly lower model performance. In this section, we will explore various AIL-ML methods that address the model cold start problem, aiming to improve the effectiveness when models begin the learning process.

After reviewing the relevant literature within the AIL-ML domain, we have identified two primary approaches to solve the cold start problem: 1) employing agents to generate an initial dataset, and 2) utilizing transfer learning and domain generalization techniques. The first approach involves using agents to generate the data that can serve as a preliminary training set. This leverages the agents' capabilities to simulate realistic data scenarios that help bootstrap the model's learning process. The second approach involves applying knowledge gained from one or more source domains to a target domain where data are scarce. This method not only addresses the scarcity of data in new applications but also enhances the model's ability to generalize across different domains, thus providing a robust foundation for model training even in the absence of extensive domain-specific data.

During the model cold start phase, a high-quality initial dataset is necessary for model training. Agents can provide or generate initial dataset, thus addressing the cold start problem. Large models can generate the data needed for initial training, enabling smaller task-specific models to begin training without data. Therefore, large models can resolve the cold start issue by supplying or creating initial training data [54]. Shuohang Wang *et al.* [53] demonstrated how large models can be used to generate annotated data, rapidly assembling an initial dataset to overcome the cold start problem. Especially in low-resource settings, the label data produced by large models provide sufficient information. Large models can short the time of acquiring initial annotated data through few-shot learning. Additionally, the cost of using large models for data annotation is significantly lower than that of human annotation, which helps to quickly acquire large-scale high-quality annotated data with limited budgets. These high-quality initial annotations can accelerate the early training process, enabling the model to quickly initiate from a cold start. Besides generating data labels, large models can also produce inferences [9]. By leveraging inferences and labels generated by large models, smaller models can gain rich contextual information and task knowledge from the start of training. This effectively addresses the cold start problem, allowing small models to quickly achieve better performance with limited training data. Large models significantly reduce the time and financial costs associated with acquiring high-quality datasets, providing a more feasible option for individuals or small organizations to utilize advanced AI capabilities [8].

The second approach to resolve the model cold start issue involves leveraging transfer learning, where knowledge from one or more well-resourced source domains is applied to a target domain that lacks sufficient data. This method not only addresses the scarcity of data in new applications but also enhances the model's ability to generalize across different domains, thus providing a robust foundation for model training even in the absence of extensive domain-specific data. Similarly, experts can utilize

domain generalization to adjust models based on diverse tasks. This method involves learning from one or several related but different domains, allowing the model to generalize well to an unseen domain. Theoretical insights from Jindong Wang and Ben-David support this approach by indicating that invariant feature representations across domains ensure the generalizability and transferability of the model [49, 50]. Consequently, experts may utilize the pretraining-finetuning strategy within transfer learning to adapt the model to new settings effectively [51].

Given the initial state M_0 and minimal or no historical data at time $t = 0$, how to utilize AIL-ML framework to address model cold start issue can be defined as:

$$M_1 = \chi(M_0, \sigma(A_0, P_{\text{gen}}), A_0, P_{\text{cold}}) \quad (8)$$

where:

- M_0 is the model’s initial state which is usually untrained or only configured.
- $\sigma(A_0, P_{\text{gen}})$ represents the data generation function, influenced by agent’s input A_0 and data generation parameters P_{gen} .
- A_0 is the agent’s input at the initial stage, influencing both the data generation and the model update process.
- P_{cold} are the parameters specifically designed for rapid adaptation during the cold start phase.
- χ is the cold start learning function, which is responsible for integrating the data generated by the agent with the learning parameters, and quickly updating the state from M_0 to M_1 .

4.2.2 Model Training

In machine learning, the model training process involves the adjustment of model parameters using optimization algorithms. This procedure involves the selection of the model’s architecture, the loss function, and the optimizer to ensure effective learning. The model’s architecture influences the model’s capacity to capture relevant patterns in the data. Moreover, loss function ensures that the model’s predictions align closely with the actual outcomes. Similarly, the choice of optimizer affects the efficiency and speed with which the model converges to a solution. Agents can leverage their deep understanding of the problem, thereby offering essential insights to enhance model performance.

Generally, AIL-ML framework integration in model training is in two ways: 1) agents use knowledge to optimize model training or 2) agents can be designed as a component of the machine learning network architecture.

Agents can leverage their knowledge to guide the design and training of models, ensuring that these models effectively capture the core patterns of the tasks. Agents can influence several aspects of model development, including selecting the appropriate model framework, loss functions, and optimization algorithms, as well as adjusting the training procedures such as the number of training iterations or epochs [41, 78]. Joris Roels *et al.* [44] developed an AIL approach to address the explosion of data sets

due to 3D technology in electron microscopy. They created an interactive graphical user interface that allows biologists to use with the framework in an intuitive and user-friendly fashion. Experts directly interact with the model through this graphical interface to evaluate the performance of various models and choose the most suitable one. Additionally, experts can select regions of interest and setting parameters to optimize the model, ensuring the efficiency and reproducibility of the algorithms.

Agents can be designed as a component of the machine learning network architecture. These agents continuously provide real-time feedback that adjusts the model’s behavior, thereby optimizing the training outcomes. Some researchers innovatively incorporated agents directly into the network architecture. Such designs allow the model to learn and adapt during training actively from agent, enhancing model’s ability to adjust internal feature representations based on agent inputs [42]. Some researchers embedded agents into the network architecture as core elements by the interactive mechanisms and feedback loops [40, 45]. Seoung Wug Oh *et al.* [40] presented a method for interactive video object segmentation where agents annotate video frames (e.g., through scribbles). These annotations are utilized by an interactive network to generate initial masks for foreground objects. The agent’s annotations not only serve as input to the interactive network but also continuously influence the network’s outputs through multiple rounds of interaction and feedback. Similarly, Yanfei Wang *et al.* [43] introduced H-Gen, an automatic H-DNN compression framework that incorporates human input as a new hyperparameter for accurate and efficient DNN generation. When the model exhibits low confidence in certain inputs during training, the agent is triggered to generate precise label data for these samples. The H-DNNs generated by H-Gen outperform the original DNNs in terms of accuracy, latency, and energy consumption, significantly improving performance in resource-constrained environments. Large model can also be used as a component of network [46, 79]. Minae Kwon *et al.* [46] integrated LLMs into reinforcement learning frameworks as proxy reward functions. They input natural language prompts into the LLM. Then LLM evaluates the behavior of reinforcement learning (RL) agents based on the prompts and produces textual outputs as reward signals. These reward signals are subsequently parsed into numerical reward signals, which are utilized by the RL agents to update their strategies and undertake new training iterations. Although designing effective prompts requires careful consideration, the contextual learning capability of the LLM allows it to capture human-like behavioral priors from minimal examples. This capability facilitates the efficient generation of reward signals that are well-aligned with the user’s objectives, thus training RL agents more effectively.

The model training process, integrating agent’s insights into it, can be defined as follows:

$$M_{t+1} = \phi(M_t, D_t, A_t, \Theta_t) \quad (9)$$

where:

- M_t and M_{t+1} represent the model states at time t and $t + 1$, respectively.
- D_t is the training dataset at time t .

- A_t includes inputs from the agent, which may suggest modifications to the model architecture, loss function, or optimization strategy.
- Θ_t encompasses the set of training parameters, which integrates training parameters with the insights provided by the agent.
- ϕ is the model update function that not only applies conventional optimization algorithms but also integrates the agent’s guidance to achieve more effective learning and improved model performance.

4.2.3 Model Iterative Refinement

The development of machine learning models is an iterative process that depends on continuous assessment and refinement. In a real-world long-term machine learning systems which are longer than months or even years, a natural feature that we should concern is that the data changes over time [80]. Therefore, when deployed for a long time, models are needed to be frequent retraining and adjustments to maintain accuracy and relevance. Furthermore, the process of evaluating discrepancies between model predictions and actual outcomes generates crucial feedback, which is fundamental to the iterative enhancement of models. AIL-ML offers robust solutions to address these challenges. In this section we will explore various AIL-ML methods that specifically focus on model iterative enhancement. AIL-ML methods facilitate the continuous integration of feedback into the learning cycle, enabling models to adapt proactively to changes in data patterns and environmental conditions. This not only helps in fine-tuning the models based on real-time data but also enhances their ability to generalize across varying contexts and over time. By embedding agents that can assess, adjust, and refine model parameters continuously, AIL-ML systems ensure that machine learning models remain effective and responsive to the evolving nature of real-world data, thereby sustaining their performance and relevance in long-term deployments.

Incorporating human feedback into model iterations significantly enhances alignment with human intentions, particularly within the field of NLP [31]. The use of AIL frameworks is essential in this context, as they significantly enhance the model’s ability to navigate complex linguistic structures, cultural subtleties, and linguistic variations. Without the involvement of human expertise, machine processing tends to be simple and rigid. This human-centric approach not only improves model capability and safety but is also indispensable for tasks where pure machine learning falls short, such as in dialogue systems where defining conversational goals without human input can lead to significant misalignments. In recent advancements, the integration of human preference feedback through RL has shown promise in refining models through iterative enhancements [27–30, 33]. This method starts with the development of a reward function trained on human feedback that targets specific aspects of a task that are important to humans. Following this, the model iterates based on the refined reward function, continually adjusting to better align with human preferences. For example, Ying Fan *et al.* proposed using online reinforcement learning to fine-tune text-to-image models. In this setup, the model continually generates new samples and

adjusts its generation strategies based on human feedback [30]. This online and iterative enhancement process heavily relies on the continuous input of human feedback, enabling gradual improvements with each iteration. The model enhances the quality and alignment of the generated images to better reflect human intentions. Direct quality assessments provided by humans train the reward function, thereby increasing both the accuracy and consistency of the model. This feedback assists in handling complex generation tasks, such as creating scenes with multiple objects or specific attributes like color, quantity, and placement, ensuring that the images accurately reflect the text descriptions. Human feedback also significantly extends the model’s generalization capability, as it incorporates a broad spectrum of scenarios and descriptions, thus improving the model’s adaptability to various applications. Further, human inputs allow for ongoing optimization, helping the model avoid local optima and adapt to new user demands in real-time, reducing training data biases and enhancing the fairness and quality of the outputs. Following a similar methodology, Daniel M. Ziegler *et al.* have refined language processing tasks with a reward model derived from human preferences, overcoming the constraints imposed by fixed evaluation metrics such as BLEU or ROUGE [33]. This strategy better aligns the model with genuine human linguistic practices and perceptions, thereby enhancing the model’s learning signals and exploratory directions, significantly boosting the efficiency of model iterations and the quality of outputs [29].

Despite the success achieved by model iteration enhancements through human feedback, reliance on human supervision introduces challenges such as the high cost of manual oversight and issues related to quality, reliability, diversity, consistency, and potential biases. In response, researchers have turned to using feedback from LLMs to enhance models for more complex tasks [35]. Canwen Xu *et al.* have developed a method known as Self-Distillation with Feedback (SDF), which utilizes feedback from LLMs for iterative enhancement and fine-tuning of models [34]. In this approach, a trained question-answering model generates four distinct responses for each input prompt. These responses are then evaluated by ChatGPT based on usefulness, relevance, accuracy, and detail, with the highest-scoring response selected for further model fine-tuning. Fine-tuning employs newly introduced low-rank adaptation modules that update only the low-rank matrices in the model’s linear layers, enabling efficient parameter tuning while avoiding the high computational costs associated with training reward models. This method enhances model performance by achieving fine-grained optimization, capturing subtle feedback differences, and reducing the risk of catastrophic forgetting. It also offers significant advantages in training efficiency and resource utilization. Given that LLMs can partially substitute for human input, some researchers, like Martin Klissarov, have proposed reinforcement learning based on feedback from large models [37]. Klissarov introduced a novel approach called “Motif,” which uses the prior knowledge of LLMs to construct intrinsic reward functions for RL agents, facilitating the learning of preferences. Researchers evaluate model outputs using LLMs, generate preference datasets, and then train reward models to fine-tune the original models. The intrinsic rewards generated by LLM significantly enhance model performance in complex tasks and guide the model to produce behaviors consistent with human intuition.

LLMs have the distinct capability to blend high-level knowledge into specialized models and ensure that model outputs are aligned with human ethical values and intentions [38]. In this context, Zhiqing Sun *et al.* [36] proposed the SELF-ALIGN method, which leverages principle-driven reasoning with the generative strengths of LLMs to enable AI agents to self-align with minimal human intervention. This method employs a set of manually defined principles to direct the LLM’s response generation, greatly diminishing the reliance on human supervisors. The team has developed 16 principles that specify the ideal characteristics of system-generated responses. These principles act as a framework for producing responses that are not only useful but also ethical and dependable. Through a process of fine-tuning, these principles are incorporated into the LLM’s parameters, allowing the model to autonomously generate responses that adhere to these guidelines, eliminating the need for direct application of the principles and examples.

Models can enhance their performance through active learning and interactive refinement, leveraging human knowledge to identify and correct their gaps, uncertainties, or errors [20, 24, 26]. Riku Arakawa *et al.* [32] proposed PrISM-Tracker, a multimodal procedure tracking framework, employs wearable sensors and state transition data for user-driven error and uncertainty resolution. This framework actively queries users to address uncertainties encountered during tracking, showcasing a method that combines active learning with time series analysis to enhance accuracy. User input allows the model to continually correct errors and optimize performance during practical usage, consistently obtaining high-quality annotated data. By dynamically updating the model, it adapts more effectively to user habits and environmental changes, reducing long-term uncertainties and enhancing the robustness and predictive accuracy of the system. Similarly in the paper [25], the authors improve the performance of semantic parsing by incorporating user feedback, thus enabling iterative model enhancement. In each iteration, the model generates preliminary SQL queries and assesses uncertainties through an error detector, subsequently generating clarifying questions for the user. User feedback is then used to confirm or correct the model’s predictions, with the model updating its current state based on this feedback and re-predicting uncertain segments. After multiple iterations, the model progressively adapts to the patterns of user feedback, minimizing unnecessary queries and improving parsing accuracy.

The iterative enhancement of the machine learning model under the AIL-ML framework can be mathematically represented by the following formula:

$$M_{t+1} = \psi(M_t, D_t, A_t, \Lambda_t) \quad (10)$$

where:

- M_t and M_{t+1} represent the model at time t and $t + 1$.
- D_t is the dataset at time t , which may evolve over time reflecting changes in data patterns.
- A_t denotes the feedback obtained from agent, evaluating the discrepancies between model predictions and actual outcomes.

- Λ_t encompasses a set of parameters guiding the model update process.
- ψ is the model update function that integrates both traditional data-driven updates and agent-based insights to adaptively refine the model in response to changing conditions.

5 Applications

5.1 Applications for General Knowledge Domain

In the domain of general knowledge within AIL-ML, various innovative applications have been developed to enhance computational experiences, making them more enriching, helpful, and adaptable to specific deployment environments.

Fig. 7 Frameworks of AIL-ML application in smart home environments. a) [32]: Overview of PrISM-Tracker architecture which utilizes a transition graph and user-provided simulated oracles to enhance the robustness and accuracy of HAR systems in procedural tracking. b) [47]: Overview of our bootstrapping method. Phase 1 involves representation learning and clustering to identify action units. Phase 2 focuses on discovering higher-level features, and Phase 3 involves deploying the activity detection method within the smart home environment. c) [20]: Listen Learner architecture, a self-supervised algorithm that detects salient acoustic events and generates classifiers for activity recognition, effectively minimizing user involvement. d) [70]: An example of how AI-to-human actuation complements an AI sensor under perception difficulty. e) [76] Overview of LLMIE-UHAR that leverages large language models and iterative evolution to realize unsupervised HAR.

In the context of intelligent home environments, the incorporation of AIL-ML is gradually reshaping the interaction dynamics between users and automated systems, enabling these systems to better understand and adapt to user behaviors through iterative feedback loops. As shown in Figure 7, this adaptation process leverages real-time

data and agent inputs to continuously refine and optimize the performance of smart home devices. Bootstrapping methods for Human Activity Recognition in smart homes initiate with passive observation, gradually building activity models through minimal supervision, thereby recognizing frequent activities with significant precision [47]. Additionally, applications such as the “Listen Learner” [20] leverage user interactions for activity recognition, minimizing user effort while enhancing system adaptability to specific environments. The PrISM-Tracker framework [32] employs wearable sensors and graph-based state transitions, coupled with user inputs, to refine procedure tracking, addressing uncertainties in real-time. The AI-to-Human Actuation [70] approach actively make user modify environmental conditions to improve the robustness of visual AI sensors, aligning system responses with human activities more accurately. Additionally, Jiayuan Gao *et al.* proposed LLMIE-UHAR [76], a method that leverages LLMs and iterative evolution to achieve unsupervised HAR. In an IoT environment, multiple smart devices generate vast streams of data. These data not only consist of raw information but also contain rich contextual and semantic information, such as the background, time, location, and interactions between devices. LLMIE-UHAR use prompt engineering to transform sensor data into textual descriptions rich in contextual information, making it comprehensible to LLMs. Then, the LLM is used for analysis and inference, enabling precise annotation of the sensor data. These applications highlight the integration of agent insights with machine learning algorithms to enhance smart home ecosystems.

In the intelligent dialogue systems domain, the focus is on refining conversational agents to offer more human-like interactions through advanced natural language processing and context management. The use of AIL-ML is key, enabling these systems to learn from user interactions and improve over time [24]. AIL-ML can not only efficiently utilize real-time conversational data for training but also dynamically adjust based on user feedback and satisfaction, leading to an improvement in both the overall model performance and user experience.

5.2 Applications for Specialized Knowledge Domain

The significance of AIL-ML is increasingly recognized in specialized fields such as medicine or healthcare [83]. Despite the promising capabilities of large language models in medicine, the enhancement of Clinical Decision Support systems and complex clinical areas requires the incorporation of human insights through AIL methodologies. As shown in Figure 8.a, in [81], clinical decision support logic summaries were provided to ChatGPT, an AI-based question-and-answer tool developed from large language models, to generate recommendations. These AI-generated recommendations were reviewed by multiple clinicians and found to be high in understanding and relevance. However, they scored lower in terms of utility, acceptance, bias, inversion, and redundancy. In applications like Medical Decision-Making, particularly with image retrieval systems, machine learning algorithms fall short of capturing the nuanced understanding of similarity as perceived by experts. This gap led to the development of a tool named SMILY [63]. It can be observed from Figure 8 that the tool allows clinicians to directly influence search algorithms, translating certain parameters into refined medical concepts for enhanced diagnostic effectiveness and algorithmic trust

Fig. 8 Frameworks of AIL-ML application for specialized knowledge domain. a) [81] A prototype of potential implementation in EHR system—AI decision support editors. b) [63] Key components of SMLY. c) [82] The workflow of the AITL system which is designed for expert to resolve the data bottleneck problem for the treatment of pancreatic cancer.

without sacrificing accuracy. This approach not only improves the diagnostic process but also enables users to adopt innovative strategies for a deeper understanding and rectification of both machine learning and human errors.

The application of AIL-ML extends to dealing with computationally intensive tasks such as subspace clustering, protein folding, and the K-anonymization of health data. In these scenarios, the exponential search space can be significantly reduced with the aid of human expertise through the heuristic selection of samples. In the context of health informatics, particularly when tackling limited datasets or rare occurrences, the limitations of automated machine learning due to insufficient training samples become evident. A study advocates for the adoption of interactive machine learning, described as algorithms that enhance their learning outcomes through interactions with agents, including humans [84]. This approach allows AIL-ML to utilize human knowledge and experience, optimizing the learning trajectories of machine learning models and thereby elevating their accuracy and efficiency.

The deployment of AIL-ML in disease diagnosis, such as Coronary Artery Disease, leverages expert insights integrated into the classification process, enhancing diagnostic accuracy [85]. This approach not only augments the interpretability and transparency of the models but also bolsters their reliability. AIL-ML applications effectively address data bottlenecks in the treatment of various diseases, including pancreatic cancer. According to Figure 8.c, by incorporating nuanced human judgments and expertise, these systems enhance the efficiency and outcomes of medical interventions, as demonstrated in recent studies [82].

6 Discussion about Limitation and Future Work

6.1 Limitation

AIL-ML, as a process-oriented paradigm, spans multiple research domains but lacks the well-defined research objectives and standardized methodologies characteristic of fields like transfer learning or domain generalization. While it is widely applied in areas such as data acquisition, model training, cold-start problems, and data annotation, AIL-ML incorporates diverse techniques, including human feedback, active learning, and LLMs. Due to the broad range of applications and the variety of techniques involved, AIL-ML methods are challenging to describe in a precise and detailed manner. Instead, they can be summarized by focusing on optimization strategies in data acquisition, processing, and model development, such as reducing annotation costs, improving data initialization, or enhancing model training through agents. This high-level abstraction provides flexibility and broad applicability but also introduces the limitation of lacking standardization in research methods. Consequently, much of the ongoing work focuses on integrating existing techniques within the AIL-ML framework, without establishing a unified technical process or evaluation criteria. Therefore, AIL-ML functions more as a guiding philosophy than as a specific technical toolkit. Future research should prioritize the development of domain-specific methodologies and standardized frameworks to enhance the consistency and practicality of AIL-ML applications.

A potential limitation of the AIL-ML framework lies in its reliance on the performance of LLMs. While LLMs provide advanced capabilities in reasoning and language understanding, their outputs in specialized domains may be inaccurate or misleading, potentially lower the overall system performance. Additionally, LLMs are often considered "black boxes," lacking transparency and interpretability. This limitation can hinder the adoption of AIL-ML in fields requiring high levels of trust and explainability, such as medical diagnostics. AIL-ML relies on a combination of human input and agent feedback, making it more dependent on the quality and reliability of the agents used within the system. This distinction highlights the need for further research into improving the transparency and accuracy of LLMs when integrated into the AIL-ML framework.

6.2 Future Directions

Reducing Bias in AIL-ML Framework. In AIL-ML, how to reduce bias is an important and valuable research direction. Currently, both LLMs and human experts are inherently biased. For instance, LLMs may exhibit selection bias by being overly sensitive to changes in input options' order or position [86] and the training data for LLMs often contains embedded social, cultural, or historical biases that can be amplified in outputs. Additionally, human experts involved in the AIL process may also have cognitive biases, which can result in unbalanced or biased knowledge being introduced into the ML. Therefore, future research must focus on developing methods to ensure unbiased knowledge injection within the AIL-ML framework. This involves not only mitigating bias at the source (from both agents like LLMs and human contributors)

but also establishing mechanisms to detect and correct biases during data annotation, model training, and feedback loops. Approaches could include designing fairer selection mechanisms, implementing diverse annotation strategies, and employing de-biasing techniques to counteract both selection and data biases. Moreover, algorithms capable of identifying and rectifying potential biases in human and LLM-based annotations will further enhance the fairness and reliability of AIL-ML systems. By systematically addressing bias, AIL-ML can improve its applicability to high-stakes domains such as healthcare and legal decision-making, where trust and explainability are important, while also promoting fairness and generalizability across diverse applications. This research direction is crucial not only for enhancing the technical performance of AIL-ML systems but also for advancing the social responsibility of AI technologies.

Enabling Agents to Handle High-Dimensional and Unstructured Data in AIL-ML. A significant research direction for AIL-ML is finding effective methods to enable agents to process high-dimensional and unstructured data. Currently, most AIL-ML systems are designed to handle low-dimensional data or natural language, with limited exploration of unstructured data types such as images, sensor signals, and acoustic data. In practical applications like smart homes and healthcare, the lack of context-awareness for these unstructured data types limits the potential of intelligent systems. Addressing this challenge by developing techniques that allow agents to handle complex, high-dimensional data can unlock new possibilities for AIL-ML, enabling more robust contextual understanding and improved performance in diverse environments. This direction holds great promise for enhancing the adaptability and intelligence of systems in fields like IoT and smart healthcare, where dealing with unstructured data is crucial.

Enhancing Collaboration Between Large Models and Humans in AIL-ML. A promising future direction for AIL-ML research is focusing on improving the collaboration between LLMs and humans. As AIL systems continue to evolve, the autonomy and collaboration mechanisms in multi-agent systems become critical. Future research can explore how to establish effective collaboration frameworks among multiple agents, including domain-specific LLMs and human experts. These agents can collaborate and share knowledge, enabling more effective handling of complex tasks. By fostering better cooperation between large models and human experts, AIL-ML systems can significantly enhance their performance and adaptability across diverse applications. This direction opens up new possibilities for optimizing human-AI interaction, making AIL systems more versatile and capable in various real-world scenarios.

7 Conclusion

Human-in-the-Loop Machine Learning (HIL-ML) has become an important research topic in machine learning research. The development and popularization of large model introduce both challenges and opportunities to this field. In this paper, we present a comprehensive survey of AIL-ML (which is also called HIL⁺-ML), providing an in-depth review of its methodologies across key stages of machine learning, including a systematic review of data collection, data initialization, data quality enhancement,

data annotation, model cold start, model training, and iterative model refinement. Furthermore, we summarize AIL-ML applications in diverse fields. Finally, we analyze the current challenges and highlight future directions. We hope that this survey will serve as a valuable resource for researchers, offering insights that encourage further exploration and development in AIL-ML.

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